

AUTOMATIC WATER PUMP CONTROL SYSTEM USING GSM MODULE AND ARDUINO: AUTOMATION OF WATER SUPPLY SYSTEM (GSMUZ08)

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Abstract. *This study focuses on the development and effectiveness of an automatic water pump control system based on a GSM module and Arduino. As an innovative solution, it aims to enhance the efficiency of water supply systems through automation. The system continuously monitors the water level, automatically activating the pump when it falls below a specified minimum threshold. Real-time messages are sent to the user via the GSM module. This work highlights the significance of emerging technologies, particularly the use of GSM modules and Arduino, in automating water supply systems. The article details the programming process, operational status of the system, and provides a comprehensive report on experimental results. The findings demonstrate high accuracy and effectiveness, showcasing how the system can improve water resource management. This survey emphasizes the importance of modern technologies in the automation of water supply systems.*

Keywords: *arduino, GSM Module, Automatic Control, Water Supply System, Water Level Sensor, Relay Module, Water Pump, Automation, Real-Time Monitoring, Fluid Level Measurement, Resource Efficiency, Water Conservation.*

Literature Analysis. The water supply system plays a vital role in modern life, as effective management is essential for agricultural, industrial, and urban infrastructure. One of humanity's fundamental needs is to ensure an adequate level of water; therefore, conserving water resources is crucial for enhancing the effectiveness and quality of control systems. This article presents an automatic water pump control system based on a GSM module and Arduino.

The system continuously monitors the water level and automatically activates the pump when it falls below a specified minimum threshold. It provides users with the ability to receive notifications via mobile devices, enabling remote management. This innovative solution aids in improving the efficiency and control of water supply systems while offering real-time information to users.

The operation of the system is straightforward: a water level sensor continuously measures the water level, and if it drops below the minimum set point, the pump is activated. The GSM module immediately informs the user, allowing them to issue commands to turn the pump on or off via text message. This article details the system's structure, reviews programming experiences, and discusses the challenges encountered along with proposed solutions.

Required materials

- 1.Arduino boards: Arduino Flour or a similar model.
- 2.Gsm module: SIM800L, to send a message through the phone.
- 3.Water level measurement sensors: liquid level to determine.
- 4.Rel which such module: pump to manage.
- 5.Water pump: Water - to pumping.

6. Power source: pump and module.

The work of the state of the system

In the system the water level is measured continuously. If specified minimum of water level dropped, then the pump is turned on. Arduino is done through the process of management, as a result, the message will be sent to the GSM module. This process works by sending messages to the sim card and provides real-time monitoring.

SMS Notifications

Arduino Automatic Water Pump Control System Functions

The Arduino automatic water pump control system performs several essential functions:

Sensor Data Reading: The Arduino receives and analyzes water level data from the sensors. This information is crucial for determining whether the water level is high or low, enabling informed decision-making.

Pump Control: The Arduino manages the relay module to activate or deactivate the pump. If the water level drops below the specified minimum, the pump is automatically triggered to start.

SMS Notifications: The Arduino sends commands to the GSM module, preparing and transmitting SMS messages to inform the user of critical situations, such as low water levels or pump activation.

Logical Programming: The system's logic ensures efficient operation by defining when to activate or deactivate the pump and when to send messages based on predefined conditions.

Monitoring and Diagnostics: The system regularly monitors the water level and notifies the user when maintenance or attention is needed, facilitating overall system performance.

As the central control unit, the Arduino ensures that all components work in harmony, providing a user-friendly interface for effective management of the water supply system.

Functions of the GSM Module

The GSM module serves several key functions:

SMS Notifications: It sends messages to the user, such as alerts for low water levels or pump activation. This is typically handled by the SIM800L module.

Receiving SMS: The module receives commands from the user, allowing for manual control of the system, such as activating or deactivating the pump.

Real-Time Monitoring: It monitors changes in water levels and provides quick updates to the user, enhancing process control.

Remote Management: This feature allows users to control the system remotely, simplifying management and improving convenience.

Safety Alerts: The module ensures system safety by sending warnings related to water levels or pump conditions.

The GSM module plays a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency of the water supply system and improving user convenience.

Device Overview: GSMUZ08

The GSMUZ08 is a device capable of remotely controlling up to eight devices, including the water pump, making it a versatile tool for water management.

GSMUZ08

Reasons for Using GSM in This Device

The primary reason for incorporating a GSM module in this device is its ability to operate wherever there is cellular signal coverage. Unlike a Wi-Fi module, which requires an internet connection, the GSM module has a broader range, making it more versatile for remote applications. This device offers several conveniences:

Time Efficiency: It minimizes wasted time, allowing users to manage the system more effectively.

Enhanced Security: Users can monitor and control the system remotely, reducing security concerns.

Convenience of Access: There is no need to be physically present at the device to operate it.

Remote Status Checking: Users can easily check the device status from different locations.

Cost Savings: When traveling far, there's no need to hire someone to manage the device (e.g., activating the water pump).

Programming Process

The process of writing Arduino code involves several key steps:

Sensor Data Reading: The system retrieves water level measurements from the sensors to gather necessary information.

Pump Control: The code includes functions to activate or deactivate the pump using a relay module.

SMS Notifications: The system sends SMS messages through the GSM module when the water level is low or when the pump is activated.

4. Key Corrections and Explanations:

GSM Initialization: Ensure you replace "your_phone_number" with the actual phone number you want to send SMS to.

Functionality:

The program initializes a software serial connection to communicate with the GSM module.

It reads the water level from the sensor and compares it to a threshold.

If the water level is below the threshold, it activates the pump and sends an SMS alert. If the level is sufficient, it deactivates the pump.

Delay: The program checks the water level every 10 seconds, which can be adjusted as needed.

SMS Format: The code sets the GSM module to SMS text mode and sends the SMS correctly by appending the message.

Additional Notes:

Make sure the GSM module is correctly connected to the specified RX and TX pins.

Ensure your Arduino board has enough power to operate both the GSM module and the pump, especially if using a relay.

```
#include <SoftwareSerial.h>
```

```
SoftwareSerial gsmSerial(7, 8); // RX, TX pins for GSM module
```

```
const int waterSensorPin = A0; // Water level sensor pin
```

```
const int relayPin = 9; // Pin connected to the relay
```

```
const int threshold = 300; // Threshold for water level
```

```
void setup() {
```

```
    pinMode(relayPin, OUTPUT); // Set relay pin as output
```

```
    gsmSerial.begin(9600); // Initialize GSM serial communication
```

```
    Serial.begin(9600); // Initialize Serial monitor for debugging
```

```
}
```

```
void loop() {
```

```
    int waterLevel = analogRead(waterSensorPin); // Read water level
```

```
    if (waterLevel < threshold) {
```

```
        digitalWrite(relayPin, HIGH); // Activate the pump
```

```
        sendSMS("Low water level! The pump is activated.");
```

```
    } else {
```

```
        digitalWrite(relayPin, LOW); // Deactivate the pump
```

```
    }
```

```
    delay(10000); // Check every 10 seconds
```

```
}
```

```
void sendSMS(String message) {
```

```
    gsmSerial.print("AT+CMGF=1\r"); // Set SMS format to text mode
```

```
    delay(100);
```

```
gsmSerial.print("AT+CMGS=\"your_phone_number\""); // Replace with your phone
number
delay(100);
gsmSerial.print(message); // Send the message
delay(100);
gsmSerial.write(26); // Send Ctrl+Z to indicate end of message
}
```

Results. The system demonstrates effective control of the water supply process. By continuously monitoring the water level, it facilitates automatic control of the pump and enables convenient messaging via GSM. Testing results indicate that the system has high accuracy in detecting water levels, and the management process is executed swiftly and reliably. The pump operates automatically based on the monitored data, ensuring efficient water resource management.

Problems and Suggestions

During the installation of the system, a couple of issues have been identified, particularly concerning the mutual dependence of the GSM module's signal strength and the sensors. To address these challenges, it is recommended to use stronger or additional power sources for the GSM module to ensure reliable communication and functionality. This enhancement can help improve the overall performance of the system and reduce the likelihood of signal-related problems.

Conclusion. The GSM module and Arduino-based automatic water pump control system serves as an innovative solution for water supply management. This system aids in resource conservation and enhances the efficiency of water usage. Future improvements are planned to further develop the system, including the addition of features such as a software interface or mobile app for more convenient management.

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